

FLAME NEWSLETTER – ISSUE 1

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

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Editorial

Welcome to **Issue 1** of FLAME's e-Newsletter!

In this Issue, you will read about fire weather and extreme fire behavior and learn how the research team of FLAME aims to advance our scientific understanding to increase awareness and preparedness for extreme wildfires.

Enjoy reading!

Theodore M. Giannaros
Principal Investigator of FLAME
IERSD/NOA
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FIRE WEATHER

Simply put, **fire weather** is weather conducive to the ignition and spread of wildfires.

Every fire needs three things to ignite and be sustained – **fuel**, **oxygen**, and **heat**. Weather can affect each of these elements. Periods of wet weather encourage the growth of vegetation, increasing fuel availability. Under high temperatures and low humidity, fuels dry out and become flammable. A fire will more likely occur under hot, dry, and windy conditions. Strong winds supply the fire with oxygen and fan the flames, pushing them towards unburnt fuels. Understanding fire weather is therefore crucial for safe and effective fire suppression operations.

Early fire weather research identified **4 critical weather elements** common to large and extreme wildfires:

- Low humidity
- Strong surface winds
- Atmospheric instability
- Drought

Humidity is a measure of the water vapor content of air. Research has shown that the general relationship between humidity and fire behavior or/and fire danger is through humidity's influence on the **moisture content of fuels**. Dead fuels constantly exchange moisture (water vapor) with the atmosphere. When the atmosphere is dry (humid) they release (take on) moisture to (from) it. Live fuels are also affected, especially under

periods of prolonged dry weather. Hence, **low humidity increases the flammability of fuels**, making them easier to ignite and carry fire. Fireline intensity, the rate of spread, and spotting probability also increase when humidity is low.

Wind is perhaps the most well-studied fire weather element. Its influence on fire behavior or/and fire danger is four-fold: **(i)** wind contributes to the exchange of moisture between fuels and the atmosphere, thus influencing the flammability of fuels, **(ii)** wind directly affects the rate of fire

spread by decreasing the angle between buoyant flames and unburnt fuels, (iii) wind increases the probability of spotting, and (iv) wind controls the flow of oxygen and other combustion products in the flaming zone, thus affecting the intensity with which fuels burn.

The **stability of the atmosphere** is one important weather element that defines if and when a wildfire will blow up. Simply put, atmospheric stability describes the resistance of the atmosphere to vertical motions; a stable atmosphere suppresses vertical motions, whereas an unstable atmosphere enhances vertical motion.

The heat released by a wildfire warms the air, which is then forced to rise, generating **updrafts**. The stability of the atmosphere controls the strength and extent of these updrafts. An unstable atmosphere enhances the updrafts generated by a wildfire, encouraging the growth of the **convective column** developing right above it. In turn, this increases combustion rates, as more oxygen is vigorously supplied to the flaming zone. As a result, the strength and depth of the convective column continue to increase, eventually leading to the **blow up** of the wildfire and the occurrence of transient fire phenomena, such as fire whirls and pyrocumulus or pyrocumulonimbus clouds.

EXTREME FIRE BEHAVIOR

The term “**extreme**” implies a level of fire behavior characteristics that ordinarily preclude any methods of direct control action. Such **fire behavior characteristics** typically include:

- High rate of fire spread
- Prolific crowning
- Massive spotting
- Strong convective column

The occurrence of extreme fire behavior is often linked strongly with **wildfire plume dynamics**. Plume dynamics refer to processes related to the growth of a wildfire’s convective column. Such processes can influence directly fire behavior by accelerating surface winds. In turn, plume

dynamics are strongly affected by the **vertical structure of the atmosphere**. Processes related to synoptic and sub-synoptic dynamics can bring down to the surface dry and high-momentum mid/upper-tropospheric air, which may produce dangerously unpredictable shifts in fire behavior.

EXTREME FIRE WEATHER AND FIRE BEHAVIOR IN GREECE

The most vivid example of the occurrence of extreme fire weather & fire behavior in Greece is the **deadly Mati wildfire** (2018). The Mati wildfire broke out on a day that synoptically was characterized by the break-down of an upper ridge and the traverse of a shortwave trough above Greece. Such synoptic conditions are considered typical of **extreme fire weather**. The presence of the upper ridge marks the persistence of dry, warm conditions that significantly increase the flammability of the available fuels. As soon as the ridge breaks down, the shortwave trough marks the occurrence of highly unstable conditions with gusty, strong winds. As a result, the Mati wildfire quickly evolved into an extreme event that could not have been controlled, characterized by very high rate of spread, prolific crowning, and highly unpredictable fire behavior. The conditions observed during the wildfire point to the occurrence of a rare firestorm.

THE FLAME PROJECT

Fire is changing because we change the conditions in which it occurs. Not all fires are harmful and not all fires need to be extinguished. However, large and destructive wildfires are today a challenge that we are not prepared for. As such wildfires occur under extreme fire weather

conditions, our role in their prevention is minor. Yet, we can do a lot to increase wildfire anticipation, preparedness, and response.

Our research project, FLAME, aims to **advance our understanding of extreme fire weather and behavior** in Greece to increase awareness and preparedness. Specific objectives include:

- To compile the climatology of critical fire weather patterns of Greece, determining their frequency, strength, and duration during a typical fire season, and verifying relationships with atmospheric teleconnections and/or SST anomalies.
- To compile a database of extreme wildfire events in Greece, examine the processes and conditions under which major transitions in fire behavior took place, and assess whether threshold conditions exist, which could be used for predicting extreme fire behavior.
- To advance the capacity of a coupled fire-atmosphere modeling system in terms of accurate fire spread prediction, by coupling a wind gust parameterization scheme with the fire spread algorithm.

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